

A PROPOSAL OF VISUAL RATING (VR) METHOD FOR SEISMIC VULNERABILITY ASSESSMENT OF EXISTING UNREINFORCED MASONRY BUILDINGS

S. M. M. Islam^{1*}, M. A. R. Bhuiyan², T. U. Mohammed³

¹Reserach Fellow and Former Jr. Research Consultant, JICA-JST-SATREPS-TSUIB Project, Housing and Building Research Institute (HBRI), Bangladesh, email: sheikh.muhammadul@gmail.com

²Professor, Department of Civil Engineering, CUET and Ex-Senior Research Consultant, JICA-JST- SATREPS-TSUIB Project, HBRI, Bangladesh, email: arbhuiyance@cuet.ac.bd

³Professor, Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering, IUT, Bangladesh, email: tarek@iut-dhaka.edu

Abstract

Bangladesh has a potential risk of future earthquakes as it is located in a tectonically active region close to the plate boundaries of the north moving Indian plate and the Eurasian plate to its north and east. A recent survey revealed that a significant part of old masonry buildings in Bangladesh are seismically vulnerable, requiring to be strengthened for future use conforming to the national building code. Seismic evaluation and retrofit of such vulnerable buildings are of great concern for a safer and more resilient urban society to future damaging earthquakes. In this regard, the current study is aimed to develop a visual screening method, as the pre-requisite step of the detailed seismic evaluation method of unreinforced masonry (URM) buildings. A visual rating (visual screening) method, considering local construction materials and, practices in URM buildings, for preparing a priority list of buildings requiring detailed seismic evaluation is proposed. Considering the seismic capacity of each load bearing masonry wall of a building a visual rating index of the building at each floor level has been developed. The fundamental characteristics, such as building type, number of stories, aspect ratio and slenderness ratio of wall, opening dimensions, level of irregularities, age of construction and physical appearance of URM building have been duly considered in the proposed method. The adequacy of the proposed method has been checked by conducting detailed seismic evaluation of a number of URM buildings. The analytical results have shown that the proposed method can be an effective and practical tool in the seismic evaluation of large masonry building stock in a short time with limited resources, and to make a priority list of URM buildings for detailed seismic evaluation.

Keywords

Unreinforced masonry building; Seismic evaluation; Visual rating method; Detailed seismic evaluation.

1.0 Introduction

In 1998, Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), U.S.A proposed the initial Rapid Visual Screening (RVS) methodology as “*Rapid Visual Screening of Buildings for Potential Seismic Hazards: A Handbook*” [1]. Many countries follow the similar RVS methodology as developed by FEMA with relevant modifications concerning their region or country where local seismic damage database is available [2]. In RVS methodology, a visible examination of buildings is done out throughout the road survey while not going in the building and will take regarding half-hour for every building. This visual investigation involves collecting fundamental characteristics of a URM building, such as building type, number of stories, soft and weak stories, opening dimensions, structural cracks, existence of irregularities in elevation and plan, year of construction, location of the building, soil type, seismic zone, appearance quality of the building, etc. Depending on the collected data, basic structural and modification factor, a structural score of URM building is computed without any information regarding the seismic capacity of the existing building. The basic structural score and modification factor of any type of building have been judged based on the damage scenario of the similar type of building in the past earthquakes. This procedure saves time and resources that can be used effectively for the buildings that need detailed assessment. In Bangladesh, such damage scenario of masonry buildings due to earthquakes is very limited and the construction practices are very different from that in USA. In this context, a visual screening (Visual Rating) method, considering local construction materials and practices in masonry buildings, for preparing a priority list of buildings requiring detailed seismic evaluation is necessary. Visual Rating (VR) method is a visual screening method that is used for rapid screening of buildings for potential seismic hazard for making a priority list of buildings for detailed seismic evaluation [3].

2.0 Methodology

The main concept of this method comes from the principle that the seismic capacity of the URM walls of a URM building should be greater than the seismic demand of the same building, considering its occupancy category, structural configuration, seismic hazard and site condition, etc., as shown in Eq. (3). The application of this method is a two-step work, such as preparation of survey datasheet and rating of the building using the proposed VR method.

2.1 Fundamentals of Seismic Evaluation Procedure

The seismic capacity of URM building is the summation of the lateral strength of each load bearing wall. The lateral strength of each wall refers to the product of cross-sectional area and corresponding shear strength shown in Eq. (1).

$$\text{Seismic Capacity} = \tau_{wi} \cdot A_{wi} \quad , \quad (1)$$

where τ_{wi} is the average shear strength of individual masonry wall, A_{wi} is the in plane cross-sectional areas of the wall.

Eq. (2) shows the seismic demand, which is the product of the total building weight (W), the response acceleration (C_a) and the reduction factor (D_s) considering the building ductility.

$$\text{Seismic Demand} = C_a \cdot D_s \cdot W \quad , \quad (2)$$

Then, for the safety of the building, the inequality as given in Eq. (3) should satisfy as,
 $\text{Seismic Capacity} \geq \text{Seismic Demand}$

$$\tau_{wi} \cdot A_{wi} \geq C_a \cdot D_s \cdot W \quad , \quad (3)$$

2.2 Visual Rating Method

The basic seismic capacity index of URM building can be obtained by dividing the lateral strength by the total floor area of the building, as presented in Eq. (4).

$$\text{Basic Seismic Capacity Index} = \tau_{wi} \frac{A_{wi}}{n \cdot A_f \cdot w} \quad , \quad (4)$$

where n is the number of stories, A_f is the floor area, w is the unit weight per floor area of the building.

2.3 Seismic Capacity Modification Factors

Several modification factors affecting the basic seismic capacity of masonry buildings are discussed below.

Wall rigidity (F_{OP}):

Opening in load bearing URM wall has significant effect on its strength and stiffness. Motivated by the results as obtained from the numerical analysis [4] using FE macro model, pier wall analysis and experiments of masonry walls, stiffness degradation factor (F_{OP}) as the function of opening area (OP) of wall is presented in Fig. 1.

Wall slenderness (F_{SR}):

The slenderness ratio affects the stability of URM walls during an earthquake, as observed in the Gorkha earthquake in 2015, and hence it is an important parameter to address out-of-plane stability of URM walls. The increase in slenderness ratio decreases the strength of URM walls [5]. Based on out-of-plane failure with marginal residual strength of URM walls, strength reduction factor (F_{SR}) as the function of slenderness ratio (SR) of URM wall is shown in Fig.2.

Aspect ratio (F_{AR}):

Aspect ratio of URM wall has significant effects on its lateral strength, stiffness and failure modes. Based on experimental results of URM walls [6] and FE analysis results of URM walls the strength reduction factor (F_{AR}) as the function of aspect ratio (H_w/L_w) of URM wall is presented in Fig.3. Table1 shows the effect of aspect ratio (AR) on failure modes [7] and lateral strength of URM walls, as motivated by experimental results of URM walls.

Deterioration effect (F_D):

The URM walls should be free from any kind of deterioration due to environmental effects. According to FEMA310 (1998) guideline [8,9], the visible crack width of 1.56 mm is defined as moderate and that of 3.125 mm is defined as severe deterioration. The weightage factor for the effect of deterioration (F_D) is given in Table 2.

Vertical irregularity (F_{IV}) and Horizontal irregularity (F_{IH}):

The irregularity factor is to modify the basic seismic capacity of structure by considering the effects of the shape complexity and the stiffness unbalance distribution, and the like on the seismic performance of URM building with engineering judgment. Weightage factors for vertical irregularity (F_{IV}) and horizontal irregularity (F_{IH}) are given in Table 2.

Building Age (F_T):

The building age factor (F_T) evaluates the effects of the structural defects such as cracking, deflection, aging, and the like, on the seismic performance of a URM building. The weightage factor for building age effect is given in Table 2.

Fig.1 Effect of wall opening on lateral stiffness

Fig.2 Effect of wall's slenderness ratio on lateral strength [5]

Fig. 3 Effect of wall's aspect ratio on lateral strength

Table 1 Effect of aspect ratio (AR) on failure modes and lateral strength of URM walls

Aspect ratio (AR)	Failure Mode Types	Factors in Terms of Strength
0 to 0.5	Bed Joint Slide	0.8
0.5 to 2.0	(Flexure, Toe Crushing, Diagonal, Bed Joint Slide) mixed modes	Linear Interpolation
2.0 or above	Rocking and/ or Rocking with Toe Crushing	0.25

Table 2 Weightage factors for deterioration, vertical and horizontal irregularities and building age [3,8,9]

	Regular	Irregular	
F_{IV}	1	0.8	
F_{IH}	1	0.9	
F_D (For individual wall)	Good	Moderate	Severe
	1	0.75	0.6
F_T	New(<15yrs)	Moderate (15 to 30yrs)	Old (>30yrs)
	1	0.95	0.9

2.4 Visual Rating Index (I_{VR})

The simplified basic seismic capacity index (Eq. (4)) of existing unreinforced masonry buildings after due consideration of the influence of strength modification factors, the visual rating index (I_{VR}) can be obtained using Eq. (5).

$$I_{VR} = [\sum_{i=1}^n (\tau_{wi} \frac{A_{wi}}{n \cdot A_f \cdot W} \cdot F_{OPi} \cdot F_{SRi} \cdot F_{ARi} \cdot F_{Di})] \cdot F_{IV} \cdot F_{IH} \cdot F_T \quad (5)$$

where $A_{wi} = (t_w \cdot l)_i$ and $A_f = l_x \cdot l_y$; t_w and l are average thickness and length of the i^{th} wall, l_x and l_y indicate the average length of building in x and y directions, respectively. The strength modification factors inside of [] shall apply for individual wall and those in the outside of [] shall apply for the whole building.

2.5 Average Shear Strength of URM Wall

The average shear strength of URM panel comprises the average bed-joint shear strength and the frictional force due to compressive force applied to it. For URM components, the average shear strength of masonry, τ_{wi} , shall be measured using the in-place shear test [10]. The general form of the average shear strength of masonry can be using Eq. (6) as

$$\tau_{wi} = \tau_0 + \mu f_{ae} \quad (6)$$

where τ_0 is the bed-joint shear strength, μ is the friction coefficient and f_{ae} is the gravity compressive stress applied to wall. In lieu of material tests, default values of the bed-joint shear strength of URM wall shall be taken not to exceed 27 psi for running bond masonry in good condition, 20 psi for running bond masonry in fair condition, and 13 psi for running bond masonry in poor condition [10]. The values of τ_0 and μ are conservatively taken as 0.10MPa and 0.40, respectively [10].

3.0 Inspection of Buildings

Visual rating of building is basically intended for rapid screening of large building stocks. So, a detailed inspection of all buildings in a stock may not be required. Simple measuring instruments like steel tape, scale, laser meter, etc. shall be used to determine the parameters. The surveyor should try his/her best to get the closest values of the parameters. The VR Index calculation requires parametric data of all floors but the inspection of the ground floor and first floor in case of inaccessibility is considerable. Parameters like wall span length, opening criteria, thickness and height of the walls indicates the values from ground floor only. The reason behind this, ground floor is typically the most vulnerable against seismic incidents. However, to understand the URM building system, possibility of soft story, and any other vertical/horizontal irregularity or any other technical reasons necessary to fill up VR survey form, the surveyor may survey other floors too. The surveyor should take necessary action to ensure entry at all crucial locations for the survey of the building. If the surveyor cannot take some parameter due to any restriction, he/she will note other data, but not complete the survey datasheet. Irrational assumptions without confirmation are not encouraged. The surveyor should be capable of understanding the whole picture of the ground floor. A sample of survey data sheet is given in Fig. 5. The application of the VR method is explained with an example given below. The example describes how the visual rating index of 2-story URM building can be estimated using the proposed VR method.

Example:

Calculation of the visual rating index I_{VR} at its ground floor of a 2-story URM residential building (Fig. 4) using the properties given as follows:

Length of each wall segment, $L_1, L_2, L_3, L_4, L_5, L_6$ and $L_7 = 4000 \text{ mm}$, thickness of each wall = 250 mm , $D_1 = 1000 \times 2200 \text{ mm}$ and $W_1 = 1500 \times 1250 \text{ mm}$. This building is 40 years old and is located in Dhaka (Seismic Zone: 2) on a medium to soft ground (Site Class: SD). The physical condition of the load bearing walls of the building is moderate, no major cracks are found. No vertical/ horizontal irregularity is found. The bed-joint shear strength of masonry panel τ_0 is 0.10 MPa. A typical floor plan of the building is shown in Fig. 4 and the survey data sample in Fig. 5.

A duly filled-in survey datasheet is given in Fig. 5. From the information as collected in the datasheet, following calculations are done to determine I_{VR} of the building.

Fig. 4 Typical floor plan of the 2-story URM building

Visual Rating (VR) Survey Sheet for Masonry Structure

Name of the Investigator & Signature: xxx
 Name of Building: B1 Dhaka
 Address: Dhaka
 DIRECTION: Y
 Date: xx/xx/xxxx

Please read carefully the selection criteria and put circle (o) in the appropriate items

No	Items	Selection Criteria	Please specify, if the value is found					Note	
1	Categories	Floor Roof System	☒ RCC	Lime Steel/Joist Composite	Concrete Steel Composite	Wood Composite	Hybrid Composite	Others	
2	No of storey (n), Height (H), (m)		Put storey number & height n = 2, H = 6m						
3	Average wall span length (l _i), (m)		l ₁ = 4m; l ₂ = 4m, l ₃ = 4m						
4	Average Opening Area, (O), (mm ²)		O ₁ = 1000 x 2200, O ₂ = 0 O ₃ = 1000 x 2200						
5	Average Thickness, (t), (mm)		t ₁ = 250, t ₂ = 250, t ₃ = 250						
6	Total length of Building, (L), (m)		L = 4m						
7	Vertical irregularity	Regular= No irregularity Irregular= Ground floor parking/Soft Storey/ Weak Storey	☒ Regular	☐ Irregular					
8	Horizontal & Mass irregularity	Regular= No irregularity Irregular= Irregular in Plan and Geometric Shape	☒ Regular	☐ Irregular					
	Water Tank & Generator	☒ No, Location (Also indicate in plan):	Center						
9	Deterioration	None= No deterioration Minor= Spalling, Damp, Efflorescence in Wall & Minor crack Severe= Major Crack (≥ 1/8") & Damage	☐ None	☒ Minor	☐ Severe				
10	Year of construction	New= less than 15 years Middle= 15-30 years Old= More than 30 years	☐ New	☐ Middle	☒ Old				
11	Other Notes								

Fig. 5 A sample of a filled-in survey datasheet

Step-1: Calculation of self-weight of the building

i) Weight of walls of the building (Unit weight of brick panel=16 kN/m³ and No. of floors is 2)

Wall Id	Length (m)	Height (m)	Opening area (m ²)	Thickness (m)	Weight (kN)
L1	4.0	3.0	1.2 x 1.0	0.250	81.0
L2	4.0	3.0	1.2 x 1.0	0.250	81.0
L3	4.0	3.0	0	0.250	96
L4	4.0	3.0	0	0.250	96
L5	4.0	3.0	1.5 x 2.1	0.250	78.4
L6	4.0	3.0	0	0.250	96
L7	4.0	3.0	1.5 x 2.1	0.250	78.4
Total weight of walls, W _w					606.8

ii) Weight of the RC floors of the building

Area of each floor = 8 x 4 = 32 m², Number of floors = 2, unit weight of concrete = 24 kN/m³ and thickness of RC slab = 150 mm.

So, the weight of floors, W_s = 2 x 32 x 0.150 x 24 = 230.4 kN.

iii) Superimposed dead and live loads

Area of each floor = 8 x 4 = 32 m², Number of floors = 2, Live load = 3.0 kN/m² and Floor finish and other loads = 3.0 kN/m².

So, the weight of superimposed dead load live load, W_{SL} = 2 x 32 x 6 = 384kN.

Total self-weight of the building, ΣW = 606.8 + 230.4 + 384 = 1231.2 kN.

Step-2: Calculation of tributary force for each wall

Total weight of floor slabs and superimposed and live load to be distributed among the walls = 230.4 + 384 = 614.4 kN. Total length of walls is 28 m. The tributary force in each wall is proportional to its length and tributary area.

Wall Id	Length (m)	Weight (kN)	Tributary weight of floor loads (kN)	Compressive force applied to wall, P _{CE} (kN)	Compressive stress applied to wall, f _{ae} (MPa)
L1	4.0	81.0	87.8	168.8	0.17
L2	4.0	81.0	87.8	168.8	0.17

L3	4.0	96.0	87.8	183.8	0.18
L4	4.0	96.0	87.8	183.8	0.18
L5	4.0	78.4	87.8	166.2	0.17
L6	4.0	96.0	175.6	271.6	0.27
L7	4.0	78.4	87.8	166.2	0.17

Step-3: Calculation of shear strength for each wall

Wall Id	Compressive stress applied to wall, f_{ae} (MPa)	Shear strength, τ_{wi} (MPa) $(0.1+0.4f_{ae})$	X-area of wall, A_{wi} (mm ²) x10 ⁶	Shear strength, Q_{mwi} (kN)
L1	0.17	0.170	1.00	169.67
L2	0.17	0.170	1.00	169.67
L3	0.18	0.174	1.00	173.51
L4	0.18	0.174	1.00	173.51
L5	0.17	0.163	1.00	163.43
L6	0.27	0.209	1.00	208.62
L7	0.17	0.163	1.00	163.43

Step-4: Calculation of modification factors for each wall

The modification factor for each wall is estimated using the expression shown in the table below.

Modification Factor	Weightage factor		
F_{OP}	$F_{OP}=1-OP(\%)/40, OP \leq 40\%$; OP: Opening Area (%) of Wall		
F_{SR}	$F_{SR} = 1.0: SR < 9; F_{SR} = -0.0625 \times SR + 1.5625: 9 \geq SR \leq 25, F_{SR} = 0: SR > 25$. SR: Slenderness Ratio of Wall;		
F_{AR}	$F_{AR} = 0.8: AR < 0.5; AR: Aspect Ratio of Wall, F_{AR} = -0.367 \times AR + 0.9835: 0.5 \leq AR \leq 2.0, F_{AR} = 0.25, AR > 2.0$.		
F_D	Good	Minor (Moderate)	Severe
	1	0.75	0.6

Wall Id	Aspect ratio (AR)	F_{AR}	Slenderness ratio (SR)	F_{SR}	Opening area (OP, %)	F_{OP}	Deterioration	F_D
L1	0.75	0.70	12	0.81	10	0.75	Minor	0.75
L2	0.75	0.70	12	0.81	10	0.75	Minor	0.75
L3	0.75	0.70	12	0.81	0	1	Minor	0.75
L4	0.75	0.70	12	0.81	0	1	Minor	0.75
L5	0.75	0.70	12	0.81	26.25	0.34	Minor	0.75
L6	0.75	0.70	12	0.81	0	1	Minor	0.75
L7	0.75	0.70	12	0.81	26.25	0.34	Minor	0.75

Step-5: Calculation of modification factors for the entire building

Modification factor	Regular	Irregular
Vertical irregularity (F_{IV})	1	0.8
Horizontal irregularity (F_{IH})	1	0.9
Age of construction (F_T)	New(<15yrs)	Old (>30yrs)
	1	0.95

Modification factors	Condition	Weightage factor
Vertical Irregularity (F_{IV})	Regular	1.0
Horizontal Irregularity (F_{IH})	Regular	1.0
F_T	Old	0.9

Step-6: Calculation of I_{VR} of the building in Y direction.

Wall Id	$I_{VRy} = \left[\sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{Q_i}{\sum W} \cdot F_{OPi} \cdot F_{SRi} \cdot F_{ARi} \cdot F_{Di} \right) \right] \cdot F_{IV} \cdot F_{IH} \cdot F_T$								
	$Q_i/\sum W$	F_{OPi}	F_{SRi}	F_{ARi}	F_{Di}	F_{IV}	F_{IH}	F_T	I_{VRy}
L5	0.13	0.75	0.81	0.70	0.75	1.0	1.0	0.9	0.12
L6	0.17	0.75	0.81	0.70	0.75				
L7	0.13	1.00	0.81	0.70	0.75				
$\sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{Q_i}{\sum W} \cdot F_{OPi} \cdot F_{SRi} \cdot F_{ARi} \cdot F_{Di} \right) = 0.137$									

4.0 Comparison with Experimental Results

In general, the VR method is based on building/structural damage data/ damage status information of the locality and it is compared to selective structural property to the physical damage state of the structural element; however, such damage data on URM buildings in our locality is not available for the direct comparison with real data. In such cases, a search of the available literatures was performed to identify experimental and analytical research works relevant to unreinforced masonry bearing-wall damage. A suite of experimental results, as reported in literature [7], of 23 masonry walls subjected different modes of loadings are considered in this comparative study. In addition, two specimens of URM walls were tested in the HBRI laboratory in Bangladesh. The experimental results showed that the governing behavior mode depends upon a number of variables including material properties, aspect ratio, and axial stress, etc. For each masonry wall specimen, seismic capacity is calculated using the proposed VR method (Eq.5) for the purpose comparison with the experiments. Table 3 shows the geometric and materials of properties of the URM walls used in the experiments. Fig. 6 shows the lateral strength of the URM walls obtained from the experiments as well as the proposed VR method, illustrating the prediction of lateral strength of URM walls using the proposed VR method.

Table 3 List of experiments with geometric and material properties of masonry wall test specimens

SI No	Reference	Specimen	Material	Loading	MPa Prism fm'	MPa Brick f'm	m Length	m Height	AR heff/L	m Thick	MPa fa
1	Anthoine et al. (1995)	High wall, first run	Brick	Quasi static cyclic	6.0	16.0	1.00	2.00	2.00	0.26	0.60
2	Anthoine et al. (1995)	High wall, first run	Brick	Quasi static cyclic	6.0	16.0	1.00	2.00	2.00	0.25	0.80
3	Magenes & Calvi (1995)	3, runs 7-12	Brick	Shake Table	8.6	18.2	1.00	2.00	2.00	0.19	0.63
4	Costley & Abrams (1996)	S1 Door Wall	Brick	Shake Table	13.5	46.4	0.44	0.81	1.85	0.09	0.23
5	Costley & Abrams (1996)	S2 Door Wall	Brick	Shake Table	13.5	46.4	0.24	0.81	3.38	0.09	0.28
6	Magenes & Calvi (1992)	MI4	Brick	Quasi static cyclic	7.9	19.7	1.50	3.00	2.00	0.38	0.69
7	Abrams & Shah (1992)	W1	Brick	Quasi static cyclic	6.3	24.0	3.66	1.83	0.50	0.20	0.52
8	Magenes & Calvi (1995)	5	Brick	Shake Table	6.2	16.0	1.00	1.35	1.35	0.25	0.63
9	Magenes & Calvi (1992)	MI2	Brick	Quasi static cyclic	7.9	19.7	1.50	2.00	1.33	0.38	0.67
10	Abrams & Shah (1992)	W3	Brick	Quasi static cyclic	6.3	24.0	1.83	1.83	1.00	0.20	0.34
11	Manzouri et al. (1995)	W1	Brick	Quasi static cyclic	13.8	21.7	2.59	1.52	0.59	0.36	1.03
12	Manzouri et al. (1995)	W2	Brick	Quasi static cyclic	15.2	21.7	2.59	1.52	0.59	0.39	0.38
13	Manzouri et al. (1995)	W3	Brick	Quasi static cyclic	17.9	21.7	2.59	1.52	0.59	0.38	0.59
14	Anthoine et al. (1995)	Low Wall	Brick	Quasi static cyclic	6.2	16.0	1.00	1.35	1.35	0.26	0.60
15	Magenes & Calvi (1992)	MI3	Brick	Quasi static cyclic	7.9	19.7	1.50	3.00	2.00	0.38	1.25
16	Magenes & Calvi (1995)	8	Brick	Quasi static cyclic	6.2	16.0	1.00	2.00	2.00	0.25	1.11
17	Magenes & Calvi (1992)	MI1	Brick	Quasi static cyclic	7.9	19.7	1.50	2.00	1.33	0.38	1.12
18	Abrams & Shah (1992)	W2	Brick	Quasi static cyclic	6.3	24.0	2.74	1.83	0.67	0.20	0.34
19	Epperson and Abrams (1989)	E1	Brick	Monotonic	12.0	57.1	2.39	1.83	0.77	0.51	0.87
20	Epperson and Abrams (1989)	E3	Brick	Monotonic	12.0	57.1	2.90	1.83	0.63	0.49	0.97
21	Epperson and Abrams (1989)	E5	Brick	Monotonic	12.0	57.1	3.48	1.83	0.53	0.49	0.56
22	Epperson and Abrams (1989)	E6	Brick	Monotonic	12.0	57.1	3.48	1.83	0.53	0.49	0.52
23	Epperson and Abrams (1989)	E7	Brick	Monotonic	12.0	57.1	3.5	1.83	0.53	0.48	0.64
24	HBRI	M1	Brick	Monotonic	3.5		1.54	1.00	0.65	0.110	0.24
25	HBRI	M2	Brick	Monotonic	3.5		1.52	1.28	0.77	0.110	0.17

5.0 Application of the VR Method to URM Buildings in Bangladesh

The proposed VR method was applied to ten existing masonry buildings in Dhaka, Bangladesh. As pointed out in the preceding section, the two-step work of the VR method, such as the duly fill-in survey datasheet and estimation of the lateral strength of the URM walls of the buildings, is followed in the application of VR method for the said buildings. The geometric and material properties of the buildings are presented in Table 4 and the physical condition of the buildings is given in Table 5. Using the information of the buildings shown in Table 4,

the VR index of each building in both horizontal directions is calculated, as shown in Table 6. As shown in Table 6, seismic vulnerability indices (I_{VR}) of the buildings, as estimated by the proposed method, predict the physical condition of the buildings shown in Table 5 in a quite logical way. The scale of vulnerability of each of the ten buildings can be judged by comparing the results of I_{VR} (Table 6) with the level of judgment of priority setting of buildings based on I_{VR} (Table 7) for seismic zone 2.

6.0 Judgment Criteria of Priority Setting for Detailed Evaluation

As discussed in the previous sections the principal objective of visual screening of URM buildings is to prepare a priority list of the buildings requiring detailed seismic evaluation rather than giving any prescriptive suggestion on seismic safety of buildings. In this context, a set of judgment criteria needs to be developed so that a professional engineer can decide on which building should be given higher priority over others for detailed seismic evaluation. Since the adequate damage data on URM buildings is not available in Bangladesh, judgment criteria of priority setting of URM buildings, using the results visual screening method has been set based on analytical results of multi-story URM building models. Motivated by the numerical results obtained using different analytical methods, such as i) method of detailed seismic evaluation. ii) linear static method, and iii) visual screening method, a preliminary set of judgment criteria of priority setting based on the results of visual rating index (I_{VR}) of URM buildings are proposed. The level of judgment criteria of URM buildings located in four seismic zones for site class D [11] is given in Table 7.

Fig.6 Lateral strength of URM walls obtained from the proposed VR method and the experiments

Table 4 Geometric and material properties of the ten existing URM buildings

Building No.	Height (m)	Wall Thickness (mm)		Length (m)		Wall Density (%) (x-dir.)/Floor Area	Wall Density (%) (y-dir.)/Floor Area	% Opening (X)	% Opening (Y)	Material
		Int.	Ext.	X	Y					
01	12	250	375	44.4	9.0	10	8.5	19.5	2.3	Brick
02	12	250	375	54.6	8.9	9.96	7.5	16.8	4.7	Brick
03	12	250	375	52.3	7.3	13.97	7.56	20.4	5.3	Brick
04	12	250	375	86.8	15.1	14	7.5	20.4	5.3	Brick
05	12	250	375	44.5	10.9	11.8	8.5	21.4	3.8	Brick
06	12	250	375	44.5	10.9	11.8	8.5	21.4	3.8	Brick
07	12	250	375	44.5	10.9	11.8	8.5	21.4	3.8	Brick
08	12	250	375	29.7	9.0	11.8	9.4	21.4	3.6	Brick

09	12	250	375	86.8	15.1	8.5	5.9	12.2	7	Brick
10	12	250	375	35.2	11.2	9.2	7.2	22.2	11.2	Brick

Table 5 Physical condition of the ten existing URM buildings

Building No.	Age (yr.)	Deterioration	Vertical Irregularity	Horizontal Irregularity
01	>30	Severe	Regular	Regular
02	>30	Minor	Regular	Irregular
03	>30	Minor	Regular	Irregular
04	>30	Severe	Regular	Irregular
05	>30	Minor	Regular	Regular
06	>30	Minor	Regular	Regular
07	>30	Severe	Regular	Regular
08	>30	Minor	Regular	Regular
09	>30	Minor	Irregular	Irregular
10	>30	Severe	Regular	Irregular

Table 6 VR index of each URM building considered in the study

Building No.	$I_{VR}(x)$	$I_{VR}(y)$	I_{VR}	Building No.	$I_{VR}(x)$	$I_{VR}(y)$	I_{VR}
1	0.19	0.27	0.19	6	0.21	0.3	0.21
2	0.15	0.16	0.15	7	0.19	0.24	0.19
3	0.16	0.11	0.11	8	0.19	0.31	0.19
4	0.16	0.11	0.11	9	0.15	0.15	0.15
5	0.21	0.3	0.21	10	0.10	0.19	0.10

Table 7. Level of judgment of priority setting of buildings based on I_{VR}

Level of Judgment	Range of I_{VR}			
	Seismic Zone 1	Seismic Zone 2	Seismic Zone 3	Seismic Zone 4
Least priority	above 0.22	above 0.36	above 0.50	above 0.65
Low priority	0.15-0.22	0.28-0.36	0.28-0.50	0.28-0.65
Moderate priority	0.10-0.15	0.17-0.28	0.17-0.28	0.17-0.28
High priority	0.08-0.10	0.10-0.17	0.10-0.17	0.10-0.17
Highest priority	Less than 0.08	Less than 0.10	Less than 0.10	Less than 0.10

7.0 Concluding Remarks

A visual rating (VR) method for estimating seismic vulnerability of existing URM buildings has been proposed in this study. This method is a two-step quick method consisting of i) collecting geometric and material data and ii) the estimation of I_{VR} of an existing URM building. The principal objective of this method is to prepare a priority list of the URM buildings requiring detailed seismic evaluation rather than giving any prescriptive suggestion on seismic safety of URM buildings. The adequacy of the method has been primarily verified with a series of experimental results of URM walls. In addition, ten existing URM buildings in Dhaka, Bangladesh have been used for application of the proposed method to compare with their physical conditions. Finally, motivated by the numerical results obtained using different analytical methods, such as i) method of detailed seismic evaluation, ii) linear static method, and iii) visual screening method, a preliminary set of judgment criteria of priority setting based on the results of visual rating index (I_{VR}) of URM buildings are proposed.

Acknowledgement

This research work was supported by HBRI in association with JICA/JST Science and Technology Research Partnership for Sustainable Development (SATREPS/TSUIB) project. The authors gratefully acknowledge all the support provided by HBRI, Bangladesh.

References

- [1] FEMA, 1998. Handbook for Rapid Visual Screening of Buildings for Potential Seismic Hazards. Federal Emergency Management Agency, US.
- [2] Federal Emergency Management Agency (US) ed., 2017. Rapid visual screening of buildings for potential seismic hazards: A Handbook. Government Printing Office.
- [3] HBRI, 2022. User's Manual on Visual Rating (VR) of Existing Reinforced Concrete Buildings for Potential Seismic Hazard in Bangladesh, Housing and Building Research Institute.
- [4] Liu, Z. and Crewe, A.2020. Effects of size and position of openings on in-plane capacity of unreinforced masonry walls, Bulletin of Earthquake Engineering, 18, pp. 4783–4812.
- [5] Alchaar, G, 2002. Evaluating Strength and Stiffness of Unreinforced Masonry Infill Structures, Construction Engineering Research Laboratory, EERDC/CERL-TR-02-1, US Army Corps of Engineers.
- [6] Chudal, P. and Maskey, P.N., 2019. The Effect of Slenderness Ratio on Seismic Performance of Unreinforced Masonry Walls. KEC Conference.
- [7] Akhaveissy, A. H., 2013. Limit State Strength of Unreinforced Masonry Structures, Earthquake Spectra 29(1), pp. 1-31.
- [8] FEMA307, 1998. Evaluation of Earthquake Damaged Concrete and Masonry Wall Buildings. Federal Emergency Management Agency, US.
- [9] FEMA310, 1998. Handbook for the Seismic Evaluation of Buildings. Federal Emergency Management Agency, US.
- [10] FEMA273, 1997. NEHRP Guidelines for The Seismic Rehabilitation of Buildings. Federal Emergency Management Agency, US.
- [11] BNBC, 2020. Bangladesh National Building Code, Housing and Building Research Institute.